

Paul Isaac Hagouel

5 June 2023

Compendium

**The Holocaust of Jewish Greeks in
Eastern Macedonia & Thrace
during World War II**

1

**The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks
in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII:
Balkan Particularities, Facts, Memory
(2013 in English)**

[Go to 1 →](#)

2

**The Fate of the Jews of Axis – Occupied
Macedonia and Thrace
(2017 in Greek)**

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3

**The Holocaust of the Jews in Eastern Macedonia & Thrace,
Southern and Central Serbia & Banat: Causae Causans,
Particularities, Cinema, Today. Brief Addendum:
Holocaust in Romania and Croatia,
Genocide of the Roma in the Balkans
(2022 in Greek)**

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4

**“Sterne” 1959 film clip
(1959 in German:)**

(you also hear Greek, Hebrew, Ladino [Judeo-Spanish] & Bulgarian)

[Go to 4 →](#)

① & ② & ③

5 June 2023
Thessaloniki

Note:

I am including three papers – presentations, one in English and two more recent in Greek. All are updated, augmented and enriched. You may follow the citations and references since most are in English, besides German, French, and Greek. You may also follow the slides in the PowerPoint presentations since most are self-explanatory. In any case, if you need further information, you may always contact me at paul231011@berkeley.edu .

Paul Isaac Hagouel
Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ

1

The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Balkan Particularities, Facts, Memory

Paul Isaac Hagouel
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Talk and Presentation at the International Conference

*Jews Across the Balkans –
History, Society and Culture
70th Anniversary
Holocaust of Jews in the Balkans*

אוניברסיטת בר-אילן
מרכז דהאן
המרכז לחברה, תרבות וחינוך במורשת יהדות ספרד
ע"ש אהרן ורחל דהאן
Bar-Ilan University
The Aharon and Rachel Dahan Center for
Culture, Society and Education in the
Sephardic Heritage

LADINO **לאדינו**
המרכז לחקר הלאדינו ע"ש נעימה ויהושע סלטי
Naime & Yehoshua Salti Center for Ladino Studies

**The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII:
Particularities, Facts, Memory**

Paul Isaac Hagouel
paul231011@berkeley.edu

Academy of Sciences and Arts
Skopje, Tuesday, October 1, 2013

*Marking 70 years since the destruction of the
Jews of the Balkans (1943-2013)*

October 1, 2013 Skopje
at the Academy of Sciences and Arts

Co-organizers:

Bar-Ilan University

The Aharon and Rachel Dahan Center for Culture, Society
and Education in the Sephardic Heritage

<http://www.dahancenter.co.il/en/>

Ashkelon Academic College, Salti Center for Ladino Studies

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Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

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CHAIRMANSHIP
2017

Switzerland

IHRA Events

International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance

Πρεσβεία της Ελβετίας, Αθήνα

Swiss Embassy, Athens

Δήμος Καβάλας

Municipality of Kavala

Academic Panel:

**The Fate of the Jews of Axis – Occupied
Macedonia and Thrace**

Talk (presentation):

Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ – Paul Isaac Hagouel

*Το Ολοκαύτωμα στην Ανατολική Μακεδονία & Θράκη, Ιστορικό
Πλαίσιο και Υπόβαθρο, Βαλκανικές Ιδιαιτερότητες*

The Holocaust in Eastern Macedonia & Thrace:

Historical Frame and Background, Balkan Particularities

Kavala, Sunday, 22 October 2017

MUNICIPALITY OF KAVALA
ΔΗΜΟΣ ΚΑΒΑΛΑΣ

The main text in pdf

PowerPoint Presentation pptx

PowerPoint Show ppsx

**Δήμος
Καβάλας**

Καβάλα κατοχή 1941

**CHAIRMANSHIP
2017**
Switzerland

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

**Πρεσβεία Ελβετίας
Αθήνα**

Το Ολοκαύτωμα στην Ανατολική Μακεδονία & Θράκη:

**Ιστορικό Πλαίσιο και Υπόβαθρο,
Βαλκανικές Ιδιαιτερότητες**

Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ

Μέλος **Ελληνικής** Αντιπροσωπείας στην **IHRA**
Διεθνή Συμμαχία για την Ανάμνηση του Ολοκαυτώματος

Μέλος Ακαδημαϊκής Ομάδας Εργασίας &
Επιτροπής Γενοκτονίας των Ρομά

Καβάλα, 22 Οκτωβρίου 2017
paul231011@berkeley.edu

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Department of Balkan, Slavic & Oriental Studies

Professors

Vlasios Vlasidis & Stratos Dordanas

The **Holocaust** of the **Jews** in Eastern Macedonia & Thrace, Southern and Central Serbia & Banat: Causae Causans, Particularities, Cinema, Today. Brief Addendum: Holocaust in Romania and Croatia, Genocide of the **Roma** in the Balkans

Paul Isaac Hagouel

Invited Lecture

within the framework of the course:

Modern Balkan History

Thessaloniki, 11 April 2022

The main text in pdf

PowerPoint Presentation pptx

PowerPoint Show ppsx

Τμήμα Βαλκανικών, Σλαβικών & Ανατολικών Σπουδών

Καθηγητές
Βλάσης Βλασίδης & Στράτος Δορδανάς
 “Σύγχρονη Βαλκανική Ιστορία”

ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ
 ΜΑΚΕΔΟΝΙΑΣ

Το **Ολοκαύτωμα** των **Εβραίων** στην **Ανατολική Μακεδονία & Θράκη**, **Νότια και Κεντρική Σερβία & Μπανάτ**: Γενεσιουργές Αιτίες, Ιδιαιτερότητες, Κινηματογράφος, Σήμερα

Κροατία, Ρουμανία, Γενοκτονία Ρομά

Genocide of the Roma
 An estimated 220,000 - 500,000 victims of Nazi persecution

 Πωλ Ισαάκ Χάγουελ
 Θεσσαλονίκη, 11 Απριλίου 2022
 paul231011@berkeley.edu

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“Sterne” 1959

film clip

[Clip avi](#)

[Clip wmv](#)

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1

The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Balkan Particularities, Facts, Memory

Paul Isaac Hagouel

Thessaloniki, Greece
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Talk and Presentation at the International Conference

*Jews Across the Balkans –
History, Society and Culture
70th Anniversary
Holocaust of Jews in the Balkans*

**The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII:
Particularities, Facts, Memory**

Paul Isaac Hagouel
paul231011@berkeley.edu

Academy of Sciences and Arts
Skopje, Tuesday, October 1, 2013

*Marking 70 years since the destruction of the
Jews of the Balkans (1943-2013)
October 1, 2013 Skopje
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Co-organizers:

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<http://www.dahancenter.co.il/en/>

Ashkelon Academic College, Salti Center for Ladino Studies

The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Balkan Particularities, Facts, Memory ¹

Paul Isaac Hagouel

Abstract

The present work focuses on the underlying seminal causes of the Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in **Bulgarian occupied Northern Greece**, in particular the regions of **Eastern Macedonia** (the cities of **Kavala, Serres and Drama**) and **Thrace** (the cities of **Alexandroupolis, Komotini and Xanthi**), along with the Annihilation of their brethren of the cities of **Didimoteixo, Nea Orestiada and Soufli** of the Evros Prefecture of Thrace **occupied by the Germans** 70 years ago. A definition of the Holocaust is given that broadens the term beyond its peak point that of the actual assassination of Jews by the Germans and some of their allies. The definition includes all past historical events and practices that fermented the path to destruction of the European and North African Jewry during the World War II as well as the now and current state practices. Starting milestones are the Preliminary Peace Treaty at San Stefano and the Peace Treaty at Berlin both of the year 1878, even though seeds of the later calamity were sowed much earlier: The sum total of seemingly unrelated historic events led inexorably to the final act of the tragedy. The root causes of the complicity of the Bulgarian governments of the time in the deportation of the Jewish inhabitants of the “New” Bulgarian territories are analyzed and, given the documentary and archival evidence presented, conclusions are reached. Also, the nation states that were created in the wake of the First World War and the ensuing Peace Treaties are shown to be fraught with all those ingredients that fertilize the national psyche to accept as legitimate racist and exclusive policies along with anti-Semitic and prejudicial ones. The distinction of Racial Anti-Semitism versus the millennia old Religious one is emphasized. Memory is an inseparable part of the Holocaust and, as such, it is both a means of Remembrance and a link with the past as well as instructive and educative for all generations and acts as a shield against Holocaust denial, revisionism and/or whitewashing of the past.

¹ The present paper is based on a **lecture** delivered at an International Conference organized by Bar-Ilan University, The Aharon and Rachel Dahan Center for Culture, Society and Education in the Sephardic Heritage, in cooperation with St. Cyril and Methodius University of Skopje. The Conference was entitled ***Jews across the Balkans – History, Society and Culture***, at the Academy of Sciences and Arts at Skopje, on Tuesday, October 1st, 2013. A concurrent **PowerPoint presentation** accompanied the lecture. Here are the links:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/r3c35s4cmn8r42r/Hagouel_Skopje_Jews%20Across%20the%20Balkans_20131001_ff.pdf

https://www.dropbox.com/s/urzrg4agxso284i/Hagouel_Jews%20Across%20the%20Balkans_Skopje_20131001_fl_ppt

During the night of March 3rd to March 4th, 1943, Bulgarian Occupation Forces swept the towns of Alexandroupolis, Komotini, and Xanthi in Thrace and the towns of Kavala, Drama, and Serres in Macedonia and, in one swift stroke, they apprehended all Jewish Greek inhabitants, rousing them in the middle of the night, confiscating their belongings and property. They assembled and held them in (mainly) tobacco warehouses. A few days later, they moved them to transitory points in Bulgaria proper². From there, they swiftly deported them outside the Bulgarian borders to the German Eastern Regions (sic), in accordance with the Dannecker – Belev Agreement signed in Sofia, on February 22nd, 1943³. This was accomplished by delivering them,

² DVD _ *Sterne (Stars)*, East Germany (DEFA) and Bulgarian Co-Production, b/w, 92 min. Feature Dir.: Konrad Wolf, Script: Angel Wagenstein, Dramaturge: Willi Brückner, Camera: Werner Bergmann Editing: Christa Wernicke, Music: Simeon Pironkow, Cast: Jürgen Frohriep (Walter), Sascha Kruscharska (Ruth), Stefan Pejtschew, Erik S. Klein (Kurt), Ivan Kondow (Ruth's father), Stiljan Kunew (the camp doctor). 16mm, English subtitles, 1959

Languages spoken: Ladino, Greek, Hebrew, German, Bulgarian

Note: Because of the infamously of Auschwitz, in the film they use it instead of the correct destination Extermination Camp of Treblinka.

<http://www.imdb.com/title/tt0053306/>

URL link of a characteristic segment of the film:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/fzzf18r0p30ummx/sterne_with_subs_trim.avi.

and [here](#).

DVD _ *Empty Boxcars*, A documentary on the triumph and tragedy of Bulgaria's response to the "Final Solution" during World War II, 1940-1943, Directed by, Screenplay by, Produced by, Ed Gaffney, 2010

<http://www.facebook.com/pages/Empty-Boxcars-a-documentary-movie-by-Ed-Gaffney/140505862662325>

³ <http://diariojudio.com/bin/forojudio.cgi?ID=8496&q=0>

Spas Tashev [stashev@diariojudio.com], *La deportación de los judíos de Macedonia, Vardar y la región del Egeo: 7ma. Parte La deportación de los judíos de las "nuevas tierras" en el año 1943, Mie Jul 11 2012 (21 Tammuz, 5772)*, 2012

<http://holocaustteaching.eu/bg/biblioteka/archivi/13-sporazumenie-po-izselvane-na-20-000-evrei-mezhdu-aleksandar-belev-i-teodor-daneker-1943-g>

Note:

Agreement between Hauptsturmführer SS [SS Captain] Theodor Dannecker and the Bulgarian Commissar for Jewish Affairs Alexandar Belev regarding the deportation of 20000 Jews from the "New" and Old Territories of Bulgaria towards the Eastern Provinces of the German Reich [Deutsches Reich]. The Agreement was signed in Sofia on February 22^d, 1943. However, Belev crossed out part of the sentence that was referring to deportations of Jews also from the main [Old Territories] of the

via Danube river boats, from Lom to Vienna. From there they were expedited by train convoys to Treblinka in occupied Poland⁴. This sealed the fate of those souls and it marked the first ever instance of mass deportations and certain subsequent annihilation of Jewish Greeks from occupied Greek territory. Actually, this marked the first time ever of deportation of Greeks with the sole intention that of their murder. This event took place a full ten days before the first death train left Thessaloniki, with destination the Auschwitz–Birkenau Concentration and Death Camp, on March 15th, 1943 on German initiative. This is factual History.

Today we are here in the heart of the Balkans and, as the title of this Conference insinuates, we celebrate the millennia old presence of Jews across the Balkans, their history, society and culture. However, another way of approaching the topic is to change the order of the actors in the title and we arrive at the following: The Balkans and the Jews: History, Society and

Kingdom of Bulgaria. The fourth and fifth intermediate assembly and concentration locales (all within Bulgaria proper) destined for the Jews in the process of deportation, with a calculated capacity to hold a total of 6000 deportees, were Gorna Dzhumaya (current name Blagoevgrad) and Dupnitsa. These were earmarked as transitory points for the Jewish Greeks of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.

⁴ (in Greek) *Alexandroupolis, Komotini, Xanthi, Kavala, Serres, Drama: The Annihilation of our Brothers & Sisters, Holocaust, Remembrance* [Αλεξανδρούπολη, Κομοτηνή, Ξάνθη, Καβάλα, Σέρρες, Δράμα: Η Εξόντωση των Αδελφών μας, Ολοκαύτωμα, Μνήμη]. Talk delivered on March 4th, 2013 to the Ladies of the Jewish community of Thessaloniki marking the 70th Anniversary of the Deportation of the Jewish Greeks from Eastern Macedonia & Thrace. A concurrent [PowerPoint presentation](#) accompanied the lecture. Here are the links:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/oyjk1pdituk14o7/Holocaust_EMacedonia_%26Thrace_Ladies_JCT_20130304p.pdf

https://www.dropbox.com/s/yjdxbn4ts9jsiv5/Paul%20Hagouel_%CE%9A%CF%85%CF%81%CE%AF%CE%B5%CF%82_%CE%99%CE%9A%CE%98_20130304_pres1_show.pps

and (also) the text in pdf [here](#), the PowerPoint [here](#), and the PowerPoint show [here](#).

Frederick B. Chary, *The Bulgarian Jews and the Final Solution, 1940-1944*, Snyder, 1972, London

Holocaust, Chronica [the Times] Magazine, issued by the Central Board of the Jewish Communities of Greece, Issue 201, Vol KΘ'(29), January-February 2006. Commemorative Issue on the Holocaust with English Supplement, Athens

http://www.kis.gr/files/chr_olokautoma_english.pdf

Culture. In this context the Jewish inhabitant is peripheral to and in the Balkans and to the nation–states that comprised (and still do) them. How did the particularities of Balkan history and of the constituent societies affect the Jews present in this peninsula and were tangential to the greater picture? Also, how did particular politics of the various Balkan nations were ancillary to fatal decisions taken by the others and vice versa? How did other ideas, politics, events and actions propagating and emanating from other European nations in the course of the last two centuries shaped, influenced and abetted the final decision of Bulgaria of the time to deport the Jewish Greeks? Balkan History of the last two hundred years is inexorably linked with the fortunes and misfortunes of the Jews in the Balkans and vice versa. Actually the litmus test of how “civilized” were the Balkan Societies was their comportment vis à vis “their” Jews.

The Balkans in the dawn of the 19th Century was roughly partitioned between the Austro–Hungarian Empire and the Ottoman Empire⁵. Without loss of generality, the lower half of Central Balkans as well as the Southern Balkans constituted part of the Ottoman Empire. Centuries old simmering discontent of the non–Muslim populations being subjugated people and the emergence and awakening of national consciousness and aspirations lead to the beginning of the disintegration of Ottoman dominance in the area. The Empire or the Sublime Porte never understood and never addressed early on and sufficiently enough all those factors that would sustain its cohesion. The same holds true also for the Austro–Hungarian Empire.

The first people to rebel and throw off the yoke of Ottoman subjugation were the Greeks in 1821. After all their national consciousness spanned millennia language wise, their lineage was traced in Hellenized Byzantium, and Orthodox Christianity, since the 4th Century CE, further cemented the nation.

⁵ http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/c/c4/Balkans_Animation_1800-2006.gif
(Note: Animated gif)

The provisional Constitution of Epidaurus in 1822 ⁶ guaranteed full freedom of Religious belief and worship. The Treaties of London of 1830 that created the Modern Greek State enshrined full emancipation for all ⁷. This principle was a constitutional mandate of all succeeding Greek Constitutions. Greece never recognized minorities only Greeks equal under the Law. Civil rights were de rigueur as opposed to group rights. The notion and reality of the Jewish Greek was fully established, when in contrast, a few years back, the Congress of Vienna in 1815 had failed to “solve” the matter of Jewish Emancipation in the Germanic States⁸.

⁶ <http://norfid.files.wordpress.com/2010/11/nomos-epidaourou-proswrinon-politeumaths-ellados-b-e8nikh-suneleusis-astros-1823.pdf>

⁷ *A_ Papers relative to the Affairs of Greece, Protocols of Conferences Held in London*, House of Commons, 1830, 340 pages, London
page 316

The London Conferences 1830 No. 25.
PROTOCOL, No. 3, of the Conference held at the Foreign Office on the 3rd of February, 1830.

Present: The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain; France; and Russia.

The Plenipotentiaries of Great Britain and Russia appreciated the justice of this demand; and it was decided that the Catholic religion should enjoy in the new State the free and public exercise of its worship, that its property should be guaranteed to it, that its bishops should be maintained in the integrity of the functions, rights, and privileges, which they have enjoyed under the protection of the Kings of France, and that, lastly, agreeably to the same principle, the properties belonging to the ancient French Missions, or French Establishments, shall be recognized and respected.

The Plenipotentiaries of the three Allied Courts being desirous moreover of giving to Greece a new proof of the benevolent anxiety of their Sovereigns respecting it, and of preserving that country from the calamities which the rivalry of the religions therein professed might excite, agreed that all the subjects of the new State, whatever may be their religion, shall be admissible to all public employments, functions, and honours, and be treated on the footing of a perfect equality, without regard to difference of creed, in all their relations, religious, civil, or political.

...
⁸ *Translation of the General Treaty, Signed in Congress, at Vienna, June 9, 1815; With the Acts Thereunto Annexed*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament, by Command of His Royal Highness the Prince Regent, House of Commons, February 1816, 300 pages, London

As expected, the Sublime Porte became apprehensive that other Christian people of the Balkans might follow suit. In addition, the Great Powers of the time, especially Russia, were also vying to expand territorially or acquire influence with the Christian populations at the expense of the Ottoman Empire. The Sublime Porte started the process of divide and rule disguising it as the carrot and the stick. A paradigm of the latter was the Danubian Principalities, Wallachia and Moldavia, precursors of modern day Romania.

ACT No. IX.

Federative Constitution of Germany ; of the 8th June 1815.

In the name of the Most Holy and Undivided Trinity.

The Sovereign Princes and free towns of Germany, animated with the mutual desire of carrying into effect the 6th Article of the Treaty of Paris of the 30th May 1814, and convinced of the advantages which will result to the safety and independence of Germany, and to the equilibrium of Europe, from their solid and lasting union, have agreed to form a perpetual Confederation, and have for this purpose invested with their full powers Their Envoys and Deputies at the Congress of Vienna, viz ;

ARTICLE XVI.

The different Christian sects in the countries and territories of the Germanic Confederation, shall not experience any difference in the enjoyment of civil and political rights.

The Diet shall consider of the means of effecting, in the most uniform manner, an amelioration in the civil state of those who profess the Jewish religion in Germany, and shall pay particular attention to the measures by which the enjoyment of civil rights shall be secured and guaranteed to them in the Confederated States ; upon condition, however, of their submitting to all the obligations imposed upon other citizens. In the mean time, the privileges already granted to this sect, by any particular State, shall be secured to them.

Note: The Federative Constitution of Germany is "In the Name of the Most Holy and Undivided Trinity"

1. October 1, 2013 **The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks** page 6 of 20
in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Particularities, Facts, Memory

Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje
Bar-Ilan University, Dahan Center

At the Treaty of Paris on March 30, 1856 they were put under the higher authority of the Porte⁹. Arduous deliberations in Constantinople by the conference of representatives of the powers resulted in the laying down of the Principles of February 11, 1856 which introduced the basic principles of civil and other rights for all inhabitants of the Principalities, something that the proclaimed policy of the rulers of the newly semi-autonomous areas was completely against¹⁰. Nonetheless, their desires prevailed and a watered down

⁹ *Treaty of Peace. General Treaty between Great Britain, Austria, France, Prussia, Russia, Sardinia, and Turkey, for the re-establishment of Peace. With three Conventions Annexed thereto.* Signed at Paris, March 30, 1856. Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons [Cmd. 2072], 1856, 36 pages, London

ARTICLE XXII.

The Principalities of Wallachia and Moldavia shall continue to enjoy under the suzerainty of the Porte, and under the guarantee of the Contracting Powers, the privileges and immunities of which they are in possession. No exclusive protection shall be exercised over them by any of the guaranteeing Powers. There shall be no separate right of interference in their internal affairs.

ARTICLE XXIII.

The Sublime Porte engages to preserve to the said Principalities an independent and national administration, as well as full liberty of worship, of legislation, of commerce, and of navigation.

The laws and statutes at present in force shall be revised. In order to establish a complete agreement in regard to such revision, a Special Commission, as to the composition of which the High Contracting Powers will come to an understanding among themselves, shall assemble, without delay, at Bucharest, together with a Commissioner of the Sublime Porte.

The business of this Commission shall be to investigate the present state of the Principalities, and to propose bases for their future organization.

¹⁰ Jack Fairey, *THE GREAT GAME OF IMPROVEMENTS: European Diplomacy and the Reform of the Orthodox Church*, Doctoral Dissertation, 2004, Toronto
Genadie Petrescu, Dimitrie Sturdza, *Acte și documente relative la istoria renascerei româniei*, Volume 2, pp. 921-951, 1889, București
<https://archive.org/details/actesidocumente04unkngoog>
https://www.dropbox.com/s/ze2nm2wa9rcswd5/Acte%20si%20documente%20relative%20la%20istoria%20renascerei%20rom%C3%A2niei%2C%20Volume%202_Protocol_Feb_11_1856_f.pdf

article supposedly guaranteeing those rights appeared at the Paris Convention between Great Britain, Austria, France, Prussia, Russia, Sardinia, and Turkey, relative to the organization of the principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia signed at Paris, August 19, 1858¹¹. The fourth paragraph of Article XLVI stated that “*Moldavians and Wallachians of all Christian confessions shall equally enjoy political rights. The enjoyment of those rights may be extended to other religions by legislative arrangements.*” So, the fate of the Jews is left to the goodwill and/or benevolent intentions (or lack thereof!) of the rulers! This phenomenon of Treaty Articles creating ambivalence and not being clear-cut and forceful will reappear, with boring regularity, in future similar treaties and conventions!

Even the thought of emancipation and granting of rights to Jews in Roumania was anathema to its rulers. They concerned themselves more with the ways to keep them apart than to integrate them into the national fabric¹². The means to achieve and maintain this apartheid were the withholding of citizenship which was the precondition for acquiring full rights. Even in Russia, Jews were second class citizens but citizens nevertheless. With the benefit of hindsight, this was the first measure that the German Reich took for disenfranchising Jewish Germans, who, automatically, reverted to just being German Jewish subjects – not citizens¹³. It was also a crucial step in Bulgarian occupied Eastern Macedonia and Thrace not to grant Bulgarian citizenship –

David Vidal, *A People Apart: The Jews in Europe 1789–1939*, page 489, Oxford University Press, 1999, New York

¹¹ *Session 1. Moldavia and Wallachia. Convention between Great Britain, Austria, France, Prussia, Russia, Sardinia, and Turkey, relative to the organization of the Principalities of Moldavia and Wallachia. Signed at Paris, August 19, 1858.* Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons [Cmd. 2454], 1859, 26 pages, London

¹² William O. Oldson, *A Providential Anti-Semitism: Nationalism and Polity in Nineteenth Century Romania*, *Memoirs of the American Philosophical Society* January 1, 1991, Vol. 193, Philadelphia

¹³ The Nuremberg Laws

<http://www.archives.gov/publications/prologue/2010/winter/nuremberg.html>
<https://www.dropbox.com/s/1f7007pm1mp4ctf/Nuremberg%20Laws.pdf>

and thus protection – to indigenous Jewish Greeks, hence putting them in a precarious position. This demonstrates that the devastation of European Jews in general and of their brethren in the Balkans in particular during WWII was an incremental process, and the cause was the sum total of the accrued minor or major steps and events.

The persecution and mistreatment of the Jews were such in Wallachia and Moldavia that, amongst others, Correspondence respecting the Persecution of Jews in Moldavia, totaling 33 pages was presented to both Houses of Parliament in the UK in 1867¹⁴. However, it seems that the mistreatment of Jews was the norm and not the exception in the area as it is reflected in the Correspondence Presented to Parliament respecting the condition and treatment of the Jews in Servia in 1867 totaling 31 pages, and in the Correspondence Presented to Parliament respecting the condition and treatment of the Jews in Servia and Roumania: 1867–76 in 1877 and totaling 372 pages¹⁵.

The Sublime Porte is not standing idle; now is the opportune time to divide and rule the Christian subjects of the Empire, mainly in the Balkans. The agitation of various majority Christian populations against the domination of the Porte, also acquiring ethno–national characteristics on the way, alarms it. In a Firman of March 12, 1870 the Porte allows the establishment of a separate Bulgarian (Christian) Orthodox Church with autonomy vis à vis the Ecumenical Patriarchate¹⁶. Via the Exarchate, the national awakening and

¹⁴ *Moldavia. Further correspondence respecting the persecution of Jews in Moldavia.* Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons Cmds [3890] [3897] [3917], 1867, 33 pages, London

¹⁵ *Correspondence respecting the condition and treatment of the Jews in Servia and Roumania: 1867-76,* Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.1742] Principalities. No. 1 (1877), 372 pages, London

Correspondence respecting the condition and treatment of the Jews in Servia, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [Cmd 3829] Servia 1867, 31 pages, London

¹⁶ The Sultan's Firman of March 12, 1870 Establishing a separate Bulgarian Christian Orthodox Church [*Exarchate*]

rallying point of Bulgarians is strengthened to the detriment of the Rum–Hellenic element¹⁷. It is interesting to note that, in 1877, Mehmed Esat Safvet Paşa mentioned in official correspondence that “*up to the time of the establishment of the Exarchate the name of Bulgaria was never used in any official documents of the Sublime Porte*”. And he added that “*the present division seems to the Ottoman Government the best suited for a good administration*”¹⁸. And, a year later in 1878, in the Preliminary Treaty of San Stefano, the Bulgarians will claim as “their” territories almost all the ones where the Exarchate was present, irrespective of the true composition of the population.

To the above we have to append the interest shown by the Powers, especially Russia sharing the Orthodox (Christian) creed, in portraying themselves as the sole protectors of the wellbeing of the Christian subjects of the Sublime Porte¹⁹. Actually their concern was overwhelmingly geopolitical using their

http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/6/65/Sultan%E2%80%99s_Ferman_for_the_establishment_of_a_Bulgarian_Exarchate_1.jpg

- ¹⁷ *The Kingdom Of Greece*, (FROM OUR OWN CORRESPONDENT), *The Times* (London, England), Thursday, Apr 14, 1870; pg. 9; Issue 26724
- ¹⁸ *Correspondence respecting the conference at Constantinople and the affairs of Turkey: 1876-77*, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons [Cmd 1641], Turkey No.2 (1857), page 351, London
Note: VIIth Protocol. - Sitting of the 26th Zilhidjé, 1923 (December 30, 1876 _ January 11, 1877)
- ¹⁹ See for example: *The Congress* (FROM OUR CORRESPONDENTS), *The Times* (London, England), Friday, Jun 28, 1878, pg. 5, Issue 29293

THE KINGDOM OF GREECE.

(FROM OUR OWN CORRESPONDENT.)

ATHENS, APRIL 7.

Two important subjects occupy the attention of the Greek Press at present. The first is a discussion concerning the conduct of the Ministers who in 1867 pushed on the Cretan insurrection and involved the Hellenic Kingdom in the catastrophe. The second is the Sultan's firman recognizing Bulgarian nationality as an element in the orthodox Church of the East.

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1. October 1, 2013 The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks page 10 of 20
in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Particularities, Facts, Memory

Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje
Bar-Ilan University, Dahan Center

professed worry for their co-religioners as the excuse for their self-serving interests. And the Jew, as usual, is left to fend for herself/himself!

The Preliminary Peace Treaty of San Stefano²⁰, in the wake of the Conclusion of the Turkish – Russian war, created a Greater Bulgaria at the expense of other native national groups which were opposed²¹. Also, the other powers were worried of a large Bulgaria under Russian influence²². So, in the Berlin Peace Congress a few months later and in the Treaty signed on July 13th, 1878, the final size of Bulgaria was much reduced²³. This left a perpetual resentment

It liberates the Bulgarians completely from the ecclesiastical domination of Greek nationality, and constitutes the Bulgarian Church as a self-governing body, with its own national archbishop or exarch and a synod ;

²⁰ *Preliminary treaty of peace between Russia and Turkey, signed at San Stefano, 19 February - 3 March 1878, (With Maps)*, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, Turkey. No. 22 (1878), 26 pages, London

Maps showing the new boundaries under the preliminary treaty of peace between Russia and Turkey, signed at San Stefano, February 19 - March 3, 1878, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons [Cmd 1975], Turkey. No. 23 (1878), 6 pages, London

Further correspondence respecting the preliminary treaty of peace between Russia and Turkey, signed at San Stefano, 19th February-3rd March, 1878, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.1995] Turkey. No. 27 (1878), 13 pages, London

²¹ *Correspondence respecting the objections raised by populations inhabiting Turkish provinces against the territorial changes proposed in the preliminary treaty signed at San Stefano, 19th February, 3rd March, 1878*, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2009] Turkey. No. 31 (1878), 64 pages, London

²² *THE SAN STEFANO TREATY: RUSSIA'S STRATEGIC ADVANTAGES. Different Articles in the Treaty Discussed - Struggling over a Disjointed Empire - The Possibility of a Congress - Liberty of Greece and Care of Bulgarians - Strength of the Army of Invasion - The Policy of Austria and England - Questions worthy of consideration* (From our Own Correspondent, Paris, Sunday, March 24, 1878), *The New York Times*, Apr 7, 1878, page 10, New York

²³ *Map showing the territory restored to Turkey by the Congress of Berlin*, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2059] Turkey. No. 37 (1878), 4 pages, London

Dispatch from the Marquis of Salisbury inclosing a copy of the treaty signed at Berlin, July 13, 1878, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2081] Turkey. No. 38 (1878), 33 pages, London

that fueled continued irredentism. By the way, intervention by major European Jewish Communities, during the deliberations, was instrumental in including clauses about religious freedom and political rights for their brethren for Serbia, Roumania and Bulgaria²⁴. Unfortunately, these remained, in most instances, dead letters. After all, the Russian Foreign Minister Alexander Mikhailovich Gorchakov had set the tone by stating and claiming that “*Jews of Serbia, Romania, and Russia could not be put in the same category with the Jews of Paris, London, Berlin, and Vienna*”²⁵. Furthermore he is recorded to have said, concerning constitutions that “*Une Constitution c’est comme une belle femme: elle n’est faite que pour être violée*”²⁶. It should be therefore not surprising that the notion to discriminate against the Jews was “ok” and, even, accepted norm. This was enhanced also by the mistreatment of Jews in Russia proper, as it is documented, just a few years later in 1882, in the Correspondence respecting the treatment of Jews in Russia, presented to both Houses of Parliament and totaling 74 pages²⁷. And, just two years before, Correspondence concerning the Condition of Mussulman, Greek, and Jewish Populations in Eastern Roumelia, totaling 322 pages, was presented at

Correspondence relating to the Congress of Berlin, with the Protocols of the Congress, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2083] Turkey. No. 39 (1878), 284 pages, London

- ²⁴ Max J. Kohler & Simon Wolf, *Jewish Disabilities in the Balkan States, American Contributions toward Their Removal, with Particular Reference to the Congress of Berlin, American Jewish Historical Society, Publications, 24 (1916), 153 pages (Note: This is a representative article of many)*
N. M. Gelber, *The Intervention of German Jews at the Berlin Congress 1878, Leo Baeck Institute Yearbook (1960) 5 (1): 221-248, 1960*
- ²⁵ Simon Dubnow, *Weltgeschichte des jüdischen Volkes Von seinen Uranfängen bis zur Gegenwart (In zehn Banden), Die Neueste Geschichte-Band IX: Das Zeitalter der ersten Reaktion und der zweiten Emanzipation (1815-1881), Autorisierte Übersetzung aus dem Russischen von Dr. A. Steinberg, Jüdischer Verlag, 1929, Berlin, page 425*
<http://ldn-knigi.lib.ru/JUDAICA/Dubnow/SDWG4-10.htm>
SERVIAN AND ROUMANIAN JEWS, The Saturday Review (Saturday review of politics, literature, science and art), May 26, 1877, 43, 1126, pg. 629
- ²⁶ *SVETOZAR TONJOROFF, BULGARIA AND THE TREATY OF BERLIN, The North American Review (1821-1940); Dec 1908; 188, 637, pg. 833*
- ²⁷ *Correspondence Respecting the Treatment of Jews in Russia, Presented to both Houses of Parliament by Command of Her Majesty, House of Commons [C.3132] [C.3250], Russia 1 (1882), 74 pages, London*

the House of Commons, UK in 1880²⁸. For decades, Roumania, for example, hindered the acquisition of citizenship by its Jewish inhabitants as an expedient for not granting rights²⁹.

With the conclusion of the Balkan wars of 1912 and 1913^{30 31} and the end of the Great War (1918)³², Bulgaria is left without the coveted access to the Aegean Sea and still fretting and grudging for the loss of the San Stefano territories, now even more so. The creation of a multitude of nation – states in the wake of the disintegration of the former Austro – Hungarian and Ottoman Empires, based on the abstract notions of ethnicity, national majorities and minorities, where the Jew belonged to none, made his/her position precarious. The inclusion of Articles on Minority Group rights in the various Peace Treaties as well as particular articles on religious liberties and other rights in specific Treaties pertinent to specific states such as the Treaty

²⁸ *Correspondence respecting the condition of the Mussulman, Greek, and Jewish populations in Eastern Roumelia*. Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [C.2552] Turkey. No. 5 (1880), 322 pages, London

²⁹ Ibid. 12

Joshua Starr, *Jewish Citizenship in Rumania (1878-1940)*, *Jewish Social Studies*, Vol. 3, No. 1 (Jan., 1941), pp. 57-80, Indiana University Press

³⁰ Note: With the end of the Balkan wars in 1913, [4 interrelated Peace Treaties](#) were signed. These were the Treaty of London, the Treaty of Bucharest, the Treaty of Athens and the Treaty of Constantinople. The following URL link gives the full text of all Treaties:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/2yk8dkz91lnfosp/Various%20Treaties_%282013%29_distr_p.pdf

[http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Treaty_of_Bucharest_\(1913\)](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Treaty_of_Bucharest_(1913))

Ratification of the Peace Treaty (in Greek & French), *Government Gazette of the Kingdom of Greece*, Issue A, Number. 229, 14 November 1913, Athens, www.et.gr [Note: It is the 1913 Treaty of Athens]

³¹ JACOB GOULD SCHURMAN, *The Balkan Wars 1912-1923, 3ed*, The Floating Press, 2008, Auckland, New Zealand

Richard C. Hall, *The Balkan Wars 1912-1923 Prelude to the First World War*, Routledge Taylor & Francis, 2000, New York

³² *Treaty of peace between the allied and associated powers and Bulgaria, and Protocol, Signed at Neuilly-sur-Seine, November 27th, 1919 [With Map]*, Presented to Parliament by Command of His Majesty, House of Commons, [Cmd. 522] Treaty Series (1920), No. 5, 95 pages, London

of Neuilly-sur-Seine for Bulgaria³³ which, actually, reiterated previous commitments as regards to those, attest two things: First, the nation – states in question in our part of the world, that is Serbia, Bulgaria and Romania, were continuously lukewarm in transubstantiating Treaty commitments and their own Constitutional mandates into deeds³⁴. Second, the Jews, by not belonging to any national group and, thus, having no particular nation – state to claim and care for them, are left powerless. The glorification of group rights at the expense and detriment of the civil rights boded dire omens for the Jewish inhabitants³⁵.

During the interwar years and up to the invasion of Greece and Yugoslavia by the German Reich in April 6, 1941, the various attitudes of discrimination and intolerance, as well as age long practices of prejudicial Anti – Judaism in Yugoslavia, Bulgaria and Romania, are molded into an underlying ensemble of mind–setting stances and negative feelings towards the Jews. Even though not officially sanctioned, they are nonetheless maintained by the state and permeated the society at large.

In the meantime, in Germany, the Reich is in power. Already millennia old religious Anti – Semitism has mutated to a racial one. This is another pseudo-scientific concoction in the quiver of the determined future assassins. This

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *Balkan Jews in the 21st Century - Bridge to Friendship and Understanding - (The Holocaust in the Southern Balkans)*, Full paper to be published at the Conference Proceedings of the Scientific Forum 70 years from the deportation of Jews from Skopje, Bitola & Štip, March 12, 2013, at the Academy of Sciences and Arts, Skopje. Organized by the Academy of Sciences and Arts, the Institute of National History and the Holocaust Fund, Skopje (Download URL link follows)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/dczn0l9wlt20eru/Hagouel_Holocaust%20in%20the%20Balkans_Skopje_March%2012_2013_f.pdf

³⁵ Carole Fink, *Defending the Rights of Others: The Great Powers, the Jews, and International Minority Protection, 1878-1938*, Cambridge University Press, 2006, New York
George Vid Tomašević, *BALKAN JEWS AND THEIR NEIGHBORS BEFORE, DURING AND SINCE THE HOLOCAUST: A Study in Ethno-Religious (and Ideological) Relations*, Humboldt Journal of Social Relations, Vol. 10, No. 1, Race & Ethnic Relations: Cross-Cultural Perspectives (FALL/WINTER 1982/83), pp. 339-363

attributable characteristic “allows” them to legally set Jews apart and deprive them of their citizenship and rights (remember Wallachia and Moldavia?). The culmination of the glorification of the Volk leads to the 1934 propaganda poster motto “Ein, Volk, Ein Reich, Ein Führer”³⁶. The Jew, the perennial outsider and the occasional standard scapegoat for all ills, does not belong to the Volk³⁷.

It is in this climate of creeping Fascism and National Socialism that Europe is heading to a crisis. The might of the German Reich wets the appetite for territorial aggrandizement and/or redress of various states. Opportunism takes hold of the foreign relations orientation of Bulgaria of the time³⁸. Realism drives the actions and reactions of Yugoslavia, sharing now a common border with the Reich. So, the first passes the Law for the Protection of the Nation³⁹ to please Hitler and the second two Anti-Semitic Laws in order to appease him⁴⁰. Furthermore, the accession of Bulgaria to the Tripartite Pact was rewarded, just a couple of months later, with the concession of Greek occupied territory that of Eastern Macedonia and Thrace⁴¹. However, Yugoslavia was

³⁶ <http://www.bnu.fr/videodisque/18/NIM18448.jpg>

<http://www.therupturedduck.com/WebPages/Documents/d306.htm>

³⁷ Lucy S. Dawidowicz, *The War Against the Jews: 1933–1945*, Bantam, 1986, New York

³⁸ *BULGARIA RENEWS TERRITORY DEMAND: Press Calls for Dobruja and an Outlet to the Aegean Sea through Greece, Expects Deal at Parley*, By C.L. SULZBERGER, THE NEW YORK TIMES, Jun 19, 1940; pg. 9

³⁹ *SOFIA DECREE LIMITS CIVIL RIGHTS OF JEWS: Law Accepted by Cabinet Is Held Sop to German Pressure*, The New York Times, Oct 9, 1940; pg. 4

http://www.archives.bg/jews/51-Anti-Semitic_Legislation_against_the_Jews_in_1941

The Law for the Protection of the Nation (ZZN, 23.01.1941) (in Bulgarian), Sofia <http://www.voininatangra.org/modules/xfsection/article.php?articleid=390>

⁴⁰ Private electronic communication of facsimiles of the two Antisemitic Laws from the *Official Gazette of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, October 5, 1940*, from the Jewish Historical Museum, Beograd, <http://www.jimbeograd.org/eng/>
YUGOSLAVIA CURBS JEWS: Forbids Those Not Citizens in 1918 to Trade in Food, The New York Times, Sep 21, 1940; pg. 4

YUGOSLAVS RESTRICT JEWS: Decree Reduces Number Who May Attend Schools, The New York Times, Oct 6, 1940; pg. 24

⁴¹ <http://diariojudio.com/bin/forojudio.cgi?ID=8178&q=0>

Spas Tashev [stashev@diariojudio.com], *La deportacion de los judios de Macedonia, Vardar y la region del Egeo: 3ra. Parte, La transferencia a Bulgaria de Macedonia del Vardar y de la Region del Egeo por parte de Alemania. Mie Jun 13 2012 (23 Sivan, 5772)*, 2012

occupied since, in the end, it renounced its association with the Reich and, thus, was invaded.

Jewish Greeks remained such albeit all the efforts of the occupiers to turn them against their Christian brethren. In early 1943 the fortunes of war for the Axis were changing inevitably for the worse⁴². The Germans became impatient and were pressing for deliverance of the Jews for transport to the Eastern Reich Territories. The Bulgarians of the time, even though not genocidists, had to repay the German largess and, thus, the fate of the Jews of the new Bulgarian Territories was sealed⁴³. The step from plain Anti – Semitism to annihilation loomed, and was proven so, very short.

This effectively concludes the events. Bulgaria today has no comparison with its old self. Neither has Romania or Serbia for that matter. Nonetheless some issues with accepting responsibility for acts of the past remain. I am optimistic that they will be resolved. In that respect, as well as for educative purposes for the younger generations, Memory and Remembrance of past events play a pivotal role. Remembrance should be a continuous dynamic process and not an instantaneous static one. That entails activities, historiography, argumentation, research, education and teaching. (For the **quantification** of memory & remembrance see⁴⁴ [in Greek])

<http://holocaustteaching.eu/en/library/archives/55-spogodba-klodius-popov-zaprisaedinyavaneto-kam-balgariya-na-teritoriite-na-vargarska-makedoniya-i-belomorska-trakiya>

⁴² Antony Beevor, *Stalingrad: The Fateful Siege: 1942–1943*, Penguin Books, 1999, New York

⁴³ Ibid 3

⁴⁴ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *Holocaust, Annihilation, Memory (Remembrance) of the Jewish Greeks of Thessaloniki, Eastern Macedonia and Thrace* [Ολοκαύτωμα, Εξόντωση, Μνήμη των Εβραίων Ελλήνων της Θεσσαλονίκης, της Ανατολικής Μακεδονίας και της Θράκης], to be published in the Proceedings of the Two-Day Conference “70 Years since the Holocaust”, Department of Political Sciences, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Saturday, April 6, 2013, English Summary – Abstract (full paper in *Greek* follows the summary in English)

Download URL links for text and PowerPoint presentation:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/5p22fag8s85d4oj/_Hagouel_Holocaust_EMacedonia_%26_Thrace_and_Thessaloniki_2013_AUTH_full_post.pdf

https://www.dropbox.com/s/fa3ky7kklnjhsjg/Paul_Hagouel_Holocaust_Thessaloniki_EMacedonia_Thrace_AUTH_PolSci_20130406_b_pps

In Greece the calamity that befell the far superior numeric wise Jewish community of Thessaloniki⁴⁵ overshadowed the destruction of the Jewish Greeks of the Bulgarian occupied territories. However, even a single death due to the Holocaust warrants Memory and Respect.

In Komotini, the Municipality erected a Monument and laid a Commemorative plaque for the more than 800 Holocaust victims in 2004. The physicians from Xanthi, Dr. Dorili Isoua (Yeshouá), my sister in law, and her husband Anastasios Karadedos financed fully the publishing of the book authored by Thrasyvoulos Papastratis and titled *From Gioumoultzina to Treblinka* in 2009⁴⁶. In Xanthi, in 2001, in successive ceremonies, the Municipality put up a commemorative plaque at the entrance of one of the tobacco warehouses where the local Jews were initially forcibly assembled.⁴⁷ The next day the book by Thomas Exarhou titled *The Jews in Xanthi (The*

⁴⁵ Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The History of the Jews of Thessaloniki & the Holocaust*, 2006, West Chester, Pennsylvania & Thessaloniki (2008)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/ozmj8h58j8v8io5/Hagouel_Thessaloniki_Holocaust_n_n-picture.pdf (in English)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/yttkjrxyq642k9f/Hagouel_Holocaust_WCUPA_2006_show.pps?m (in English) and [here](#)

https://www.dropbox.com/s/i58leisp25s0ras/Hagouel-Hol_USConsulate_2008_color_show.pps?m in Greek) and [here](#)

Paul Isaac Hagouel, *The History of the Jews of Salonika & the Holocaust – an Exposé, Sephardic Horizons* (Editor: Judith Roumani) Volume 3, Issue 3, Fall 2013,

<http://www.sephardichorizons.org/Volume3/Issue3/hagouel.html>

https://www.dropbox.com/s/474zcyjv6z9gzqg/%282013%29_in_Sephardic_Horizons_The-History-of-the-Jews-of-Salonika-and-the-Holocaust-An-Expos%C3%A9_f.pdf

⁴⁶ Komotini:

Thrasyvoulos Papastratis [Θρασύβουλος Παπαστρατής], *Από τη Γκιουμουλτζίνα στην Τρεμπλίνκα. Ιστορία των Εβραίων της Κομοτηνής [From Gioumoultzina to Treblinka. The History of the Jews of Komotini]*, Cultural and Development Center of Thrace [Πολιτιστικό Αναπτυξιακό Κέντρο Θράκης (Π.Α.ΚΕ.ΘΡΑ.)], 2009, Xanthi, Thrace

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Komotini_holocaust_memorial_c.jpg

⁴⁷ Xanthi:

Thomas Exarhou [Θωμάς Εξάρχου], *Οι Εβραίοι στην Ξάνθη (Ο Κόσμος που χάθηκε αλλά δεν ξεχάστηκε) [The Jews in Xanthi (The World that was lost but not forgotten)]*, Cultural and Development Center of Thrace [Πολιτιστικό Αναπτυξιακό Κέντρο Θράκης (Π.Α.ΚΕ.ΘΡΑ.)], 2001, Xanthi, Thrace

http://www.kis.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=294&Itemid=116

http://www.empros.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=11355:2012-11-20-13-16-09&catid=64:2011-11-28-12-49-31&Itemid=172

world that was lost but not forgotten) was presented. The sponsors were the aforementioned couple from Xanthi in major part and the Central Board of Jewish Communities in Greece in minor part.

For the more than 2000 victims to the Holocaust from Kavala, a monument was erected in the cemetery grounds⁴⁸. The Drama Municipality erected a monument in honor of its 1200 Jewish victims in 1999⁴⁹. The Serres Municipality erected a plaque and issued a proclamation – declaration with which it acknowledges March 4th of every year “as the day of remembrance of the Holocaust of the citizens of Serres of Jewish religious descent” (600 victims)⁵⁰.

In comparison, in Bulgaria proper, 66 years later, at the initiative of Ester Georgieva [Др. Естер Георгиева] of the Southwestern University of Blagoevgrad, a Memorial Plaque was set at the Metzoutsilistnia Center [Междуучилищния център] from where the trains, that were carrying 993 Jews from “Aegean Thrace”, had departed, to find their foul fate at Auschwitz (!). Note that the word Greece is completely absent and that Treblinka became Auschwitz . . .⁵¹

Our presence here proves that the past is remembered and an era of mutual respect and understanding has dawned, hopefully for eternity.

I thank you very much.

Paul Isaac Hagouel

48 Kavala: We have the testimony of **Sabetai Tsimino** who survived forced labor battalion work inside “Old” Bulgaria proper. The segment is taken from the *Empty Boxcars* (see Note 2) with the kind permission of Professor Ed Gaffney:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/7z5d4xa8kdptsvt/Sabetai_Tsimino.avi

http://www.kis.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=288&Itemid=111

49 Drama:

http://www.kis.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=286&Itemid=114

50 Serres:

http://www.kis.gr/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=297&Itemid=106

51 Gorna Dzhumaya (Горна Джумая) – present day Blagoevgrad in Bulgaria

http://dariknews.bg/view_article.php?article_id=368982

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<http://www.fas.nus.edu.sg/hist/about/hisjf.htm>

I thank with appreciation and esteem *His Excellency Ambassador Mr. Harris Lalakos*, Head of the Greek Liaison Office at Skopje, and *Mrs. Anna Lalakos* for their support and hospitality extended to me and Sabrina Hagouel during our stay at Skopje. It is always nice to feel at home away from home.

*Jews Across the Balkans –
History, Society and Culture
70th Anniversary
Holocaust of Jews in the Balkans*

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**The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII:
Particularities, Facts, Memory**

Paul Isaac Hagouel
paul231011@berkeley.edu

Academy of Sciences and Arts
Skopje, Tuesday, October 1, 2013

PowerPoint Presentation Download URL links:

pptx [here](#) and ppsx [here](#)

Paul Hagouel received his B.E. “*summa cum laude*” and his M.S. (in Electrical Eng.) from New York University in 1972 & 1973 respectively. He received his Ph.D. (in Electrical Eng. & Computer Sciences) from the University of California, Berkeley in 1976. He is an independent researcher in the fields of History of Modern Greece, History of the Holocaust, Vichy France, Human Rights & Religious Freedoms, and Comparative Religious Studies, mainly Christianity and Judaism. His father Leon was a KL Auschwitz–Birkenau survivor (**Nr. 118633**) and his mother Yvette was rescued by the Righteous **Zoe Morou** and **Danae Kadoglou – Pavlidou**.

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"Plamenka Trajkovska"
Sephardic and Macedonian
Traditional Music

Dr. Nivi Gomel, Bar-Ilan University

Zionist Discourse in Communal Pamphlets in Ladino from Salonica and Palestine

Dr. Aleksandra Twardowska, Nicolaus Copernicus University

Linguistic Features of Rafael Kamhi's Judeo-Spanish Document "Borders of Macedonia"

13:30-14:30

Lunch

14:30-16:30

SESSION 7: Holocaust and Rescue

Chairman: Prof. Ephraim Hazan, Bar-Ilan University

Dr. Paul Isaac Hagouel, Thessaloniki

The Annihilation of Jewish Greeks in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace during WWII: Particularities, Facts, Memory

Dr. Gideon Greif, Shem Olam: Faith and the Holocaust

Institute for Education, Documentation and Research

Greek Jewish Prisoners in Auschwitz – Some Unique Aspects

Dr. Stephen Suleyman Schwartz, Center for Islamic Pluralism

The Myth of Bulgarian Rescue of Jews and Reality of Bulgarian Complicity in the Destruction of Macedonian Jewry

Dr. Ofer Muchtar, Ashkelon Academic College

"Between Incomprehensible Evil" and a Moral Code of Honor – The Rescuing of the Albanian Jews during the Holocaust

Dr. Rachel-Shelly Levy-Drummer, Bar-Ilan University

and Mr. Leka Reznqi, Pristina, Kosova

The first "Righteous among the Nations" delivered to a Muslim from Kosova – Mr. A. Reznqi, for saving Dr. H. Abravanel, and the Ongoing Relationship between the Families

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